

A Zener-Stroh Crack in A Fiber-Reinforced Composite Material

Z. M. Xiao, B. J. Chen and H. Fan
School of Mechanical & Production Engineering
Nanyang Technological University
Republic of Singapore
E-Mail: mzxiao@ntu.edu.sg

Abstract

Matrix cracking is a major pattern of failure of composite materials. Crack can form in the matrix during manufacturing, or be produced during loading, especially during cyclic loading. To accurately predict the fracture behavior of a crack in a composite, the interaction of the crack with the surrounding inclusions should be fully investigated. Having a different mechanism from the conventional Griffith crack, the Zener-Stroh crack was first proposed by Zener in 1948. In his model, a pileup of edge dislocations that were stopped at an obstacle, such as a grain boundary (Fig.1 (a)), could coalesce into a crack nucleus. Besides Zener's mechanism of micro crack initiation, there are some other variants. One was presented by Cottrell (1958) as shown in Fig.1 (b), where piled-up dislocations on two intersecting slip planes can coalesce into a micro crack. The other variant proposed by Kikuchi (1981) is given in Fig.1 (c) which shows a particle at a grain boundary in a stressed solid, concentrated stress fields exist near the ends of the particle, slip is thus nucleated in these regions. Dislocations of one sign move away from the region, leaving stationary dislocations of the opposite sign behind to form a crack near the particle. This case is the experimental background for the current study.

Zener-Stroh crack is the crack complementary to the well-known Griffith crack. Physical parameters that are symmetric for the Griffith crack are anti-symmetric for the Zener-Stroh crack and vice versa. For instance, a Griffith crack dislocation distribution along the crack plane is anti-symmetric. This dislocation distribution gives rise to a symmetric crack plane traction stress. The Zener-Stroh crack has an anti-symmetric crack plane traction stress which arises from a symmetric crack plane dislocation distribution. In this paper, the interaction between a Zener-Stroh crack and surrounding cylindrical fibers in a fiber-reinforced composite material has been investigated. The crack is located in the matrix and near a fiber, while the influence of other fibers on the crack is considered through the three-phase composite cylinder model, as shown in Fig.2. Using the solution of stress field for a single dislocation in a three-phase cylinder as the Green's function, the crack is represented by a continuous distribution of dislocations. A set of singular integral equations are thus formulated and solved numerically. The stress intensity factor on the crack tip due to crack-inclusions interaction is calculated. The results show that the volume concentration of fibers has non-negligible influence on the stress intensity factor of the crack.

Key words: Crack, stress intensity factor, inclusion, interaction, self-consistent three-phase model.

1. Introduction

In composite materials, to accurately predict the fracture behavior of a crack in a composite, the interaction of the crack with the surrounding inclusions should be fully investigated. In the past three decades, quite a number of research work on the above mentioned topic have been carried out. To name a few, the interaction between a crack and a circular inclusion in a sheet under tension was studied by Tamate [1]. An elastic circular inclusion interacting with two symmetrically placed collinear cracks was investigated by Hsu and Shivakumar [2]. Sendekyj [3] studied the problem of a crack located between two rigid inclusions. The investigation for a crack near an elliptic inclusion was carried in terms of body force method by Nisitani, Chen and Saimoto [4]. Erdogan, Gupta and Ratwani [5] first considered the interaction between an isolated circular inclusion and a line crack embedded in infinite matrix. As commented by Erdogan et. al. [5], their model is applicable to the composite materials which contain sparsely distributed inclusions. For composites filled with finite concentration of inclusions it is commonly understood that the stress and strain fields near the crack

depend considerably on the microstructure around it. However, to treat the problem based on all details of the microstructure of a real composite would be too complicated. One notable simplified model is the self-consistent three-phase model used by Christensen and Lo [6], Luo and Weng [7-8] in studying effective moduli of composite materials. Unlike the two-phase model where the inclusion is embedded in the infinitely extended pure matrix, the three-phase model considers that in the immediate neighborhood of the inclusion, there is a layer of matrix material acting on. But at certain distance the average influence of the heterogeneous medium can be represented by the smeared property of the composite. Thus, for the problems of which the interest is in the field near the inclusion and crack, it can reasonably be accepted as a good model.

Having a different mechanism from the Griffith crack, the Zener-Stroh crack was first proposed by Zener [9]. In his model, a pileup of edge dislocations that were stopped at an obstacle, such as a grain boundary (Fig.1(a)), could coalesce into a crack nucleus. Besides Zener's mechanism of micro crack initiation, there are some other variants. One was presented by Cottrell [10] as shown in Fig.1(b), where piled-up dislocations on two intersecting slip planes can coalesce into a micro crack. The other variant proposed by Kikuchi [11] is given in Fig.1(c) which shows a particle at a grain boundary in a stressed solid, concentrated stress fields exist near the ends of the particle, slip is thus nucleated in these regions. Dislocations of one sign move away from the region, leaving stationary dislocations of the opposite sign behind to form a crack near the particle. This case is the experimental background for the current study. Stress, displacement, dislocation density and stress intensity factor were compared between Griffith crack and Zener-Stroh crack in a homogeneous material by Weertman [12]. Due to the displacement loading mechanism, the total sum of the Burgers vectors of the dislocations b_T within a Zener-Stroh crack does not equal zero. The crack tip where the dislocation enters the Zener-Stroh crack is called blunt tip, while the other tip is called sharp tip. The crack propagation is always initiated from the sharp tip. This kind of micro crack was often observed in metal matrix composite materials.

Fig. 1 (a) Zener's mechanism of crack initiation; (b) Cottrell's model of crack initiation; (c) Anti-Zener-Stroh crack model

2. The Physical Problem and Formulation

The physical problem to be investigated in the current paper is shown in Fig.2 (a), where a Zener-Stroh crack is initiated near a circular inclusion (a fiber) in a fiber-reinforced composite. For the case shown in Fig.2, the sharp crack tip is on the right-hand side and the left crack tip is blunt. We denote this case as Case I. While when the sharp tip is on the right, the problem is denoted as Case II. Both cases have been considered in our numerical examples shown in Section 5. The formulations are parallel to both cases. In order to consider the effect of the surrounding inclusions (other fibers) on the crack, the three-phase composite model discussed in the previous section is employed, so the original problem is made to be equivalent to Fig.2 (b), where the 2-dimensional version of the three-phase model consists of three concentric cylindrical layers with the outer one being extended to infinity.

Fig. 2 A Zener-Stroh crack in a fiber reinforced composite material and the three-phase cylinder model

The inner region $r \leq a$ (Phase “1”) is the fiber inclusion with radius a and elastic properties κ_1 ($\kappa_1 = 3 - 4\nu_1$ with ν_1 the Poisson's ratio) and μ_1 , the intermediate layer (Phase “2”) is the pure matrix material with elastic properties κ_2 and μ_2 , occupies the annular region $a \leq r \leq b$. The outside layer (Phase “3”) is the composite material with effective elastic moduli κ_3 and μ_3 , occupies the outer infinite region $r \leq b$. The internal and external radii of the intermediate matrix-phase a and b being related to each other by $(a/b)^2 = c$, here c is the volume concentration of the fibers in composite. The effective moduli of the composite κ_3 and μ_3 are calculated by the method of Christensen and Lo [6]. The Zener-Stroh matrix crack is along the radial direction and located in Phase 2 (the pure matrix material). In order to reduce the number of parameters involved in discussion, we concentrate on the influence of the net dislocations inside the crack on the stress intensity factor at crack tip, so it is assumed that the elastic system is free of external mechanical loading. It is worth to mention that the problem can be solved similarly even with external mechanical loading.

The boundary conditions of the problem are:

In the far field,

$$\sigma_{xy} = 0, \quad \sigma_{yy} = 0. \quad (1a,b)$$

At the interface,

$$[\sigma_{xy}] = 0, \quad [\sigma_{yy}] = 0. \quad (2a,b)$$

At the crack surface,

$$\sigma_{xy} = 0, \quad \sigma_{yy} = 0, \quad t_1 \leq x \leq t_2, \quad (3a)$$

$$[\sigma_{xy}] = 0, \quad [\sigma_{yy}] = 0, \quad x < t_1, \text{ or } x > t_2. \quad (3b)$$

where $[f]$ is the jump of the function f .

In order to solve the problem, the equivalence between a crack and a pile-up of dislocations is employed. Let $B_x(x)$ and $B_y(x)$ be the gliding and climbing dislocation densities along the crack line (t_1, t_2) . Using the stress field solution of a single edge dislocation in a three-phase composite [13] as Green functions, the tractions at $(x, 0)$ due to those dislocations are written as

$$\sigma_{yy}(x,0) = \frac{2\mu_2}{(\kappa_2 + 1)\pi} \left[\int_{t_1}^{t_2} \frac{B_y(\xi)}{\xi - x} d\xi + \int_{t_1}^{t_2} k_1(x, \xi) B_x(\xi) d\xi \right], \quad (4a)$$

$$\sigma_{xy}(x,0) = \frac{2\mu_2}{(\kappa_2 + 1)\pi} \left[\int_{t_1}^{t_2} \frac{B_x(\xi)}{\xi - x} d\xi + \int_{t_1}^{t_2} k_2(x, \xi) B_x(\xi) d\xi \right]. \quad (4b)$$

With the aid of the above equations, the traction free conditions on the upper and lower crack surfaces (i.e., boundary conditions (3a, b)) are written in terms of B_x , B_y as

$$\frac{1}{\pi} \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \frac{B_y(\xi)}{\xi - x} d\xi + \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \frac{1}{\pi} k_1(x, \xi) B_y(\xi) d\xi = 0, \quad t_1 \leq x \leq t_2, \quad (5a)$$

$$\frac{1}{\pi} \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \frac{B_x(\xi)}{\xi - x} d\xi + \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \frac{1}{\pi} k_2(x, \xi) B_x(\xi) d\xi = 0, \quad t_1 \leq x \leq t_2, \quad (5b)$$

Moreover, the dislocation densities $B_x(x)$ and $B_y(x)$ must satisfy

$$\int_{t_1}^{t_2} B_y(\xi) d\xi = b_y^T, \quad (6a)$$

$$\int_{t_1}^{t_2} B_x(\xi) d\xi = b_x^T. \quad (6b)$$

where b_x^T and b_y^T are the total sums of Burgers vectors of the net distributed dislocations inside the Zener-Stroh crack. Equations (5a, b) are the standard singular equations with Cauchy type kernels $k_1(x, \xi)$, $k_2(x, \xi)$ which are given by[13]

$$\begin{aligned} k_1(x, \xi) = & \frac{A+B}{2(x-a^2/\xi)} + A \frac{\xi^2 - a^2}{\xi^3} \frac{a^2}{(x-a^2/\xi)^2} \left(\frac{\xi^2}{a^2} - \frac{\xi^2 - a^2}{x\xi - a^2} \right) \\ & - \frac{A+B}{2x} - \frac{1}{2\xi} \frac{a^2}{x^2} \left[A \left(2 \frac{\xi^2}{a^2} - 1 \right) + B - 2N \right] - A \frac{a^2}{x^3} - N b_0 \frac{a}{x^2} \\ & - \frac{1}{2a} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left\{ 2b_n \left(\frac{x}{a} \right)^n + b_n n \left(\frac{x}{a} \right)^n - [b_n(n-1) - b_{-n}] \left(\frac{x}{a} \right)^{(n-2)} \right. \\ & \left. - 2Ab_{-n} \left(\frac{a}{x} \right)^n + Ab_{-n} n \left(\frac{a}{x} \right)^n + [Ab_{-n}(n+1) + Bb_n] \left(\frac{a}{x} \right)^{(n+2)} \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (7a)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} k_2(x, \xi) = & \frac{A+B}{2(x-a^2/\xi)} + A \frac{a^2}{(x-a^2/\xi)^2} \left(\frac{x-\xi}{\xi^2} \frac{\xi^2 - a^2}{x\xi - a^2} \right) - \frac{A+B}{2x} \\ & + A \frac{a^2}{x^3} - \frac{1}{2a} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left\{ b'_n n \left(\frac{x}{a} \right)^n - [b'_n(n-1) + b'_{-n}] \left(\frac{x}{a} \right)^{(n-2)} \right. \\ & \left. - \frac{B-A}{2\xi} \frac{a^2}{x^2} - Ab'_{-n} n \left(\frac{a}{x} \right)^n + [Ab'_{-n}(n+1) - Bb'_n] \left(\frac{a}{x} \right)^{(n+2)} \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (7b)$$

where

$$A = \frac{1-m}{1+m\kappa_2}, \quad B = \frac{\kappa_1 - m\kappa_2}{\kappa_1 + m}, \quad C = \frac{\kappa_3 - l\kappa_2}{\kappa_3 + l}, \quad D = \frac{1-l}{1+l\kappa_2}, \quad (8)$$

$$m = \mu_1/\mu_2, \quad l = \mu_3/\mu_2, \quad N = \frac{\kappa_1 - 1 - m(\kappa_2 - 1)}{\kappa_1 - 1 + 2m}.$$

and a_n, b_n, a'_n, b'_n are calculated from the follow two sets of equations:

$$-a_n + \frac{1}{D} b_n = \frac{1}{\beta} \delta_{n0} + \beta^{n+1} \alpha^{2n+2} + (n+1)(\beta^2 \alpha^2 - 1) \beta^{n-1} \alpha^{2n}, \quad n \geq 0 \quad (9a)$$

$$\frac{1}{A}a_{-n} - b_{-n} = \delta_{n1} - \beta^{1-n} + (n-1)(1-\beta^{-2})\beta^{1-n}, \quad n \geq 1 \quad (9b)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & D(n-1)a_n - [C\alpha^{2n} + (1-C)\delta_{n0}]a_{-n} - [(n-1) - (N-1)\delta_{n0}]\alpha^2 b_n \\ & + [1 + (N-1)\delta_{n0}]\alpha^2 b_{-n} \\ & = [(D-C)\frac{1}{\beta} + \frac{2N}{\beta}\alpha^2]\delta_{n0} + (C + 2D\beta^2\alpha^2)\beta^{n-1}\alpha^{2n} \\ & + 3D(n+1)(\beta^2\alpha^2 - 1)\beta^{n-1}\alpha^{2n} - D(n+1)\beta^{n+1}\alpha^{2n+2} \\ & - 2(-1)^n D(\beta^2\alpha^2 - 1)\beta^{n-1}\alpha^{2n}C_{-3}^n + \frac{D(1-C)}{1-D}\alpha^2\delta_{n1}, \quad n \geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (9c)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & (n+1)a_{-n} + \alpha^{-2n}a_n - A(n+1)\alpha^2 b_{-n} - B\alpha^2 b_n \\ & = -A(n+1)\beta^{1-n}\alpha^2 - B\beta^{-(n+1)}\alpha^2 + 3A(n-1)(\beta^2 - 1)\beta^{-(n+1)}\alpha^2 \\ & + 2A(-1)^{n+1}(\beta^{21} - 1)\beta^{-(n+1)}\alpha^2(1-\delta_{n1})(1-\delta_{n2})C_{-3}^{n-3} + 2A\alpha^2\delta_{n1}, \quad n \geq 1 \end{aligned} \quad (9d)$$

and

$$-a'_n + \frac{1}{D}b'_n = \frac{1}{\beta}\delta_{n0} - \beta^{n+1}\alpha^{2n+2} + (n+1)(\beta^2\alpha^2 - 1)\beta^{n-1}\alpha^{2n}, \quad n \geq 0 \quad (10a)$$

$$\frac{1}{A}a'_{-n} - b'_{-n} = -\delta_{n1} + \beta^{1-n} + (n-1)(1-\beta^{-2})\beta^{1-n}, \quad n \geq 1 \quad (10b)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & D(n-1)a'_n + [C\alpha^{2n} + (1-C)\delta_{n0}]a'_{-n} - [(n-1) - (N-1)\delta_{n0}]\alpha^2 b'_n \\ & - [1 + (N-1)\delta_{n0}]\alpha^2 b'_{-n} \\ & = (D-C)\frac{1}{\beta}\delta_{n0} + (C - 2D\beta^2\alpha^2)\beta^{n-1}\alpha^{2n} \\ & + 3D(n+1)(\beta^2\alpha^2 - 1)\beta^{n-1}\alpha^{2n} + D(n+1)\beta^{n+1}\alpha^{2n+2} \\ & - 2(-1)^n D(\beta^2\alpha^2 - 1)\beta^{n-1}\alpha^{2n}C_{-3}^n + \frac{D(1-C)}{1-D}\alpha^2\delta_{n1}, \quad n \geq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (10c)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & (n+1)a'_{-n} - \alpha^{-2n}a'_n - A(n+1)\alpha^2 b'_{-n} + B\alpha^2 b'_n \\ & = A(n+1)\beta^{1-n}\alpha^2 - B\beta^{-(n+1)}\alpha^2 + 3A(n-1)(\beta^2 - 1)\beta^{-(n+1)}\alpha^2 \\ & + 2A(-1)^{n+1}(\beta^{21} - 1)\beta^{-(n+1)}\alpha^2(1-\delta_{n1})(1-\delta_{n2})C_{-3}^{n-3} - 2A\alpha^2\delta_{n1}, \quad n \geq 1 \end{aligned} \quad (10d)$$

in which

$$\alpha = \frac{a}{b}, \beta = \xi/a, C_{-3}^n = \frac{(-3)(-4)\dots(-3-n+1)}{n!}, \quad (11)$$

and δ_{ni} is the kroneker delta.

Once the dislocation densities $B_x(x)$ and $B_y(x)$ have been solved from Eqs. (5), (6) together with Eqs.(7) and (8), the stress fields in Phase 2 can be obtained from Eq.(4). Thus the stress intensity factor (SIF) of the crack can be evaluated accordingly.

3. Solution Procedures of the Integral Equations

To shift the integral interval from (t_1, t_2) to $(-1, 1)$ in the integral equations (5) and (6), let

$$x = \frac{t_2 - t_1}{2}t + \frac{t_2 + t_1}{2}, \quad \xi = \frac{t_2 - t_1}{2}s + \frac{t_2 + t_1}{2}. \quad (14)$$

Equations (5a,b) are rewritten in terms of s, t as:

$$\frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-1}^1 \frac{B_y(s)}{s-t} ds + \int_{-1}^1 \frac{1}{\pi} k_{11}(t,s) B_y(s) ds = 0, \quad -1 \leq s, t \leq 1 \quad (15a)$$

$$\frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-1}^1 \frac{B_x(s)}{s-t} ds + \int_{-1}^1 \frac{1}{\pi} k_{22}(t,s) B_x(s) ds = 0, \quad -1 \leq s, t \leq 1 \quad (15b)$$

where

$$k_{11}(t,s) = \frac{t_2 - t_1}{2} k_1 \left(\frac{t_2 - t_1}{2} t + \frac{t_2 + t_1}{2}, \frac{t_2 - t_1}{2} s + \frac{t_2 + t_1}{2} \right), \quad (16a)$$

$$k_{22}(t,s) = \frac{t_2 - t_1}{2} k_2 \left(\frac{t_2 - t_1}{2} t + \frac{t_2 + t_1}{2}, \frac{t_2 - t_1}{2} s + \frac{t_2 + t_1}{2} \right). \quad (16b)$$

and equations (6a,b) are similarly rewritten as

$$\int_{-1}^1 B_y(s) ds = \frac{2b_y^T}{t_2 - t_1}, \quad (17a)$$

$$\int_{-1}^1 B_x(s) ds = \frac{2b_x^T}{t_2 - t_1}. \quad (17b)$$

Since the whole crack is located in Phase 2 (the pure matrix material), the singularities on the both crack tips should be $-\frac{1}{2}$. As a result, the two dislocation density functions $B_x(x)$ and $B_y(x)$ must have $-\frac{1}{2}$ singular behaviors on the both crack tips. Let

$$B_x(x) = w(x)F_x(x), \quad B_y(x) = w(x)F_y(x), \quad (12)$$

where $F_x(x)$ and $F_y(x)$ are bounded functions in $t_1 \leq x \leq t_2$, and

$$w(x) = (x - t_1)^{-\frac{1}{2}} (t_2 - x)^{-\frac{1}{2}}. \quad (13)$$

Following the method developed by Erdogan and Gupta (1972), we get the discretized forms of (15) and (17):

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{n} F_y(s_k) \left[\frac{1}{s_k - u_r} + k_{11}(u_r, s_k) \right] = 0, \quad (18a)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{n} F_x(s_k) \left[\frac{1}{s_k - u_r} + k_{22}(u_r, s_k) \right] = 0, \quad (18b)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{n} F_y(s_k) = \frac{b_y^T}{\pi}, \quad \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{n} F_x(s_k) = \frac{b_x^T}{\pi}, \quad (18c,d)$$

in which

$$s_k = \cos \frac{\pi}{2n} (2k - 1), \quad u_r = \cos \frac{\pi r}{n}, \quad k = 1, \dots, n, \quad r = 1, \dots, n - 1. \quad (18e)$$

Equations (18a) and (18c) provide a system of n linear algebraic equations to determine $F_y(s_1), \dots, F_y(s_n)$; while (18b) and (18d) provide another system of n linear algebraic equations to determine $F_x(s_1), \dots, F_x(s_n)$. Once the functions $F_x(x)$ and $F_y(x)$ are solved, the dislocation density functions $B_x(x)$ and $B_y(x)$ can be evaluated from Eqs.(12).

With the solution of the dislocation density functions obtained, the Mode I and Mode II stress intensity factors on the blunt (left) and sharp (right) crack tips as shown in Fig.2 (Case I) are then given by [14]

$$K_I^B = - \lim_{\xi \rightarrow t_1} \frac{2\mu_2 \sqrt{2\pi}}{\kappa_2 + 1} \sqrt{\xi - t_1} B_y(\xi) = - \frac{2\mu_2 \sqrt{\pi}}{(\kappa_2 + 1) \sqrt{(t_2 - t_1)/2}} F_y(-1), \quad (19a)$$

$$K_{II}^B = -\lim_{\xi \rightarrow t_1} \frac{2\mu_2 \sqrt{2\pi}}{\kappa_2 + 1} \sqrt{\xi - t_1} B_x(\xi) = -\frac{2\mu_2 \sqrt{\pi}}{(\kappa_2 + 1) \sqrt{(t_2 - t_1)/2}} F_x(-1), \quad (19b)$$

$$K_I^S = \lim_{\xi \rightarrow t_2} \frac{2\mu_2 \sqrt{2\pi}}{\kappa_2 + 1} \sqrt{t_2 - \xi} B_y(\xi) = \frac{2\mu_2 \sqrt{\pi}}{(\kappa_2 + 1) \sqrt{(t_2 - t_1)/2}} F_y(1), \quad (19c)$$

$$K_{II}^S = \lim_{\xi \rightarrow t_2} \frac{2\mu_2 \sqrt{2\pi}}{\kappa_2 + 1} \sqrt{t_2 - \xi} B_x(\xi) = \frac{2\mu_2 \sqrt{\pi}}{(\kappa_2 + 1) \sqrt{(t_2 - t_1)/2}} F_x(1). \quad (19d)$$

where the superscripts “B” and “S” represent the left and right crack tips, respectively.

4. Example Calculations and Discussions

For the numerical examples given in this section, the stress intensity factors (SIFs) of the crack are normalized by

$$K_I^0 = \frac{2\mu_2 b_y^T}{(\kappa_2 + 1) \sqrt{\pi(t_2 - t_1)/2}}, \quad K_{II}^0 = \frac{2\mu_2 b_x^T}{(\kappa_2 + 1) \sqrt{\pi(t_2 - t_1)/2}}, \quad (20)$$

they are the Mode I and Mode II SIFs at the sharp crack tip of the same size Zener-Stroh crack with the same Berbers vectors (b_x^T , b_y^T) in a homogeneous materials, respectively. As the interaction between a crack and a single inclusion has been studied by many researchers as discussed in the introduction, in our current example calculations, we concentrate on studying the influence of the volume fraction of inclusions on the behavior of crack.

Two typical types of composite materials are chosen for the examples:

$$\text{Type I: } m = \mu_1 / \mu_2 = 0, \quad \kappa_1 = 1.8, \quad \kappa_2 = 1.6, \quad (21a)$$

$$\text{Type II: } m = \mu_1 / \mu_2 = 23, \quad \kappa_1 = 1.8, \quad \kappa_2 = 1.6, \quad (21b)$$

in which $\kappa_i = 3 - 4\nu_i$ ($i = 1, 2$). The first composite material is actually an elastic matrix with certain voids (to represent a composite with “soft” inclusions), while the second one is a real fiber-reinforced material (a composite with “harder” inclusions). The size and location of the Zener-Stroh matrix crack is defined by the parameters t_1 and t_2 as

$$t_1 = 1.05a, \quad t_2 = 1.35a. \quad (22)$$

Corresponding to different volume fraction of inclusions $c = (a/b)^2$, the effective moduli of the composite (Phase 3) is evaluated according to Christensent & Lo[6].

Table 1 Normalized SIFs at the Blunt Tip

c	Type I Material: $\mu_1 = 0$		Type II Material: $\mu_1 = 23\mu_2$	
	K_I^B / K_I^0	K_{II}^B / K_{II}^0	K_I^B / K_I^0	K_{II}^B / K_{II}^0
0.00	-1.461	-1.550	-0.690	-0.649
0.05	-1.420	-1.545	-0.691	-0.655
0.10	-1.372	-1.540	-0.692	-0.663
0.15	-1.314	-1.533	-0.693	-0.673
0.20	-1.243	-1.525	-0.694	-0.685
0.25	-1.155	-1.515	-0.696	-0.699
0.30	-1.045	-1.502	-0.697	-0.715
0.35	-0.905	-1.486	-0.701	-0.733
0.40	-0.729	-1.464	-0.710	-0.752
0.45	-0.504	-1.438	-0.721	-0.772
0.50	-0.213	-1.404	-0.739	-0.791

For the case when the sharp crack tip is at right (the sharp tip is pointing away from the inclusion), the normalized Mode I and Mode II stress intensity factors (SIFs) at the blunt crack tip versus the volume fraction c of the inclusions in both types of materials are listed in Table 1. It is found that the SIFs at the blunt tip are always negative. This result is consistent to our discussion in the introduction, i.e., the propagation of a Zener-Stroh crack is always along the sharp crack tip. Therefore, in the forgoing numerical discussion, we chiefly concentrated ourselves on studying the SIFs at the sharp crack tip (the right-handed crack tip in Fig. 2 (b)).

For the case when the sharp crack tip is at left (the sharp tip is towards to the inclusion), the normalized Mode I and II SIFs at the sharp tip in the elastic matrix with voids (Type I material) are depicted in Figs. 3 and 4. While Figs. 5 and 6 show the Mode I & II SIFs of the sharp crack tip when the crack is in fiber-reinforced material (Type II material). For comparison, the results calculated based on the two-phase model (a crack interacting with a single inclusion) are also displayed in the figures. It can be clearly observed that as the fiber (or void) concentration is very dilute (small volume fraction c), the present solutions approach to those of the two-phase model. When the inclusion fiber concentration increases, the stress intensity factors decrease for the void case and increase for the fiber case.

Fig. 3 Normalized Mode I SIF at the sharp tip versus c in an elastic matrix with voids

Fig. 4 Normalized Mode II SIF at the sharp tip versus c in an elastic matrix with voids

Fig. 5 Normalized Mode I SIF at the sharp tip versus c in a fiber-reinforced composite material

Fig. 6 Normalized Mode II SIF at the sharp tip versus c in a fiber-reinforced composite material

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